

The Diffusion Control in Sol-Gel Transformation

A. AWAD, F. EL-CHEIKH and A. SHAKER

Chemistry Department, Faculty of Science, Sohag, Egypt

Manuscript received 8 January 1979, revised 12 October 1979, accepted 17 March 1980

Sodium alginate sol can be converted into ionotropic gel through the diffusion of a di- or trivalent metal ion. The kinetics of this process can be studied by two different methods. The first is the analytical method in which the decrease of the divalent metal ion concentration with time during the exchange process with sodium alginate sol is followed complexometrically. It is found that the rate of gel formation is greater at first during the primary gel membrane formation, and it depends on both the electrolyte and the sol concentration. The rate then decreases during the further gel growth and becomes constant whatever the concentration of the electrolyte is. This may be attributed to the diffusion control through the primary gel membrane.

The second method is the drop density method in which the rate of density variation of a sol drop during its contact with the electrolyte solution is taken as a measure of ionotropic gel growth. The drop density method is carried out at different temperatures, and the rate of growth is found to increase by raising temperature. The activation energy is calculated and found to have the values between (13-20 k.j./Mole).

SODIUM alginate is a poly-electrolyte, it consists of D-Mannuronic and L-guluronic acids¹.

Sodium alginate sol can be converted into ionotropic gel by the reaction with divalent or trivalent metal ions :

The sol-gel transformation is studied from the kinetic point of view. Ionotropic gels²⁻⁷ can be formed by different methods depending on the way of diffusion of the electrolyte, either by ascending or descending technique which leads to the formation of gel disc, or by the radial diffusion of electrolyte which leads to the formation of a gel drop.

By using both techniques, the sol-gel transformation can be studied kinetically. The transformation of a sol drop to a gel has been studied by Awad *et al*⁸.

In the present investigation, the kinetic studies are carried out by two different methods :

(a) *The drop density method* in which the variation of the sol drop density with time is taken as a measure of the rate of transformation. The gel formation is a partial discharge, and a partial dehydration process, which must lead to a change in density.

(b) *The analytical method* in which the concentration of the electrolyte used as a crosslinking material for the alginate molecule, changes with time. The

decrease in the electrolyte concentration can be followed analytically.

Experimental

(a) *Materials :*

All materials used are of chemical grade. The water is double distilled. The temperature is controlled within 0.1° using an ultrathermostat.

(b) *Measurements and Calculations :*

Different sodium alginate sols are prepared by dissolving the proper amount in bidistilled water⁹. The water has to be stirred strongly, and then the solid alginate is added, otherwise, it gives a plumpy solution which swells with difficulty.

In the drop density method, a sol drop is allowed to fall from a small funnel. The sol drop floats on the electrolyte, as its density is smaller than that of the electrolyte containing the divalent cations. The sol drop floats till its density attains that of the electrolyte. At this time the drop starts to sink.

The value of $\left(\frac{d\sigma_s}{dt}\right)$, the rate of the increase of the drop density is taken there as a function of the gel growth. Thus :

$$\frac{\sigma_s - \sigma_e}{\Delta t} = K V$$

where (σ_e) is the electrolyte density and

(σ_s) is the sol density. The

For each sol and electrolyte concentration, the following precautions are taken into consideration to maintain the size of the sol drop constant as far as possible :

- (1) The use of the same dropper.
- (2) The height of the sol in the dropper as well as the distance from the dropper to the surface of the electrolyte is kept constant.

In the analytical method, a long wide tube of 1.5 cm radius is covered with a very thin layer of Na-alginate and then 2/3 of the tube is filled with the sol which is covered with CuSO₄ solution. As soon as copper sulphate solution comes in contact with the sol, a very thin gel membrane is promptly formed at the sol electrolyte interface which prevents their mixing. The change in the electrolyte concentration with time is followed by complexometric titration using titriplex¹⁰. Before each titration, air is bubbled in the electrolyte to ensure homogeneity of the electrolyte concentration above the sol to avoid the concentration gradient formed during the sol-gel transformation which takes place by the exchange process between sodium ions of the alginate sol and Cu²⁺ cations in the electrolyte. The value of $\left(\frac{-dC}{dt}\right)$ is thus the rate of the gel formation.

Results and Discussion

The density method results :

When a sol drop is allowed to fall into a divalent metal ion solution, a primary gel membrane which preserves the shape of the drop is formed. This drop remains at the electrolyte surface for a certain time through which the sol drop density grows up slowly to that of the electrolyte due to the Cu²⁺ ion diffusion into the sol drop through the primary membrane. The drop then begins to sink. The time consumed for the sol drop to start sinking down (t) is measured for different sol concentrations, and different electrolyte concentrations at different temperatures (30°, 40°, 50°, 60° and 70°).

The value $\frac{\sigma_e - \sigma_s}{\Delta t}$ is taken as function of the growth rate of the gel (rate of the sol-gel transformation).

Although the variation of the sol drop density (σ_s) with time is expected to be nonlinear during the formation of the primary gel membrane yet the value of $\frac{d\sigma_s}{dt}$ represents the velocity of this process.

So, the value of $\left(\frac{d\sigma_s}{dt}\right)$ can be practically considered as a function of the sol-gel transformation rate.

By varying the concentration of the electrolyte, the value of σ_s is controlled. The time (t) at which the drop starts to sink is plotted for the different electrolyte concentrations versus σ_s . The slope of the lines obtained is thus a function of the gel growth rate $\frac{d\sigma_s}{dt}$.

By repeating the experiment at higher temperatures 30°, 40°, 50°, 60° and 70°, it was found that the rate of the formation of the primary membrane as well as the further gel growth are enhanced very much. The slope obtained from growth plot $\left(\frac{d\sigma_s}{dt}\right)$ for sol 2% and CuSO₄ electrolyte (c.f. Figures 3, 4) was about 0.0028 at 30° and 0.01 at 70°.

The heterogeneous exchange reactions between Na⁺ and Cu²⁺ ions (or any divalent cation), can thus be treated using the variation of density with time. The reaction, like many other heterogeneous reactions, was found to obey the power function.

$$V = K C^n \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

where (V) is the reaction velocity, (C) is the concentration of the varying reacting species, (K), and (n) are constants. As mentioned before $\left(\frac{\sigma_e - \sigma_s}{\Delta t}\right)$ can be considered as a function of V. So, by logarithming equation (1) we get.

$$\log V = K' + n \log C$$

$$\text{or } \log \left(\frac{\sigma_e - \sigma_s}{\Delta t}\right) = K' + n \log C.$$

Actually, by plotting $\log \left(\frac{\sigma_e - \sigma_s}{\Delta t}\right)$ versus $\log C$, of the electrolyte, (as the varying species), straight lines were obtained with (n) value around (0.5). This value can be imagined physically as the order of the exchange reaction with respect to the divalent electrolyte (Fig. 5).

Fig. 1. The variation of Cu²⁺ cation concentration with time during the exchange, with different sol concentrations t=25° 1-1.0%, 2-1.5% and 3-2.0%.

Fig. 2. The variation of Cu^{2+} concentration with time during the exchange with 2% sol. The initial concentration of Cu^{2+} are 1- 0.02M, 2- 0.06M and 3- 0.12M, $t=25^\circ$.

Fig. 5. The $\log \frac{\sigma_e - \sigma_s}{\Delta t}$ against $\log C$ plots for 2% sol in CuSO_4 solutions, at temperatures, 1-30°, 2-40°, 3-50°, 4-60° and 5-70°.

Fig. 3. The density of the sol drop (1%) with time in CuSO_4 solutions of different concentrations at temperatures 1-30°, 2-40°, 3-50°, 4-60° and 5-70°.

Fig. 4. The density growth of the sol drop 2% with time in CuSO_4 solutions of different concentrations at temperatures 1-30°, 2-40°, 3-50°, 4-60° and 5-70°.

By finding out different values of $\left(\frac{d\sigma_s}{dt}\right)$ for a definite sol and electrolyte concentration at different temperatures, the activation energy of the process (E) can be calculated (Table 1). From this table, it is clear that the value of the activation energy, lying in the range (13–20 K.J./Mole), indicates that the process is a diffusionaly-controlled one.

TABLE 1—ACTIVATION ENERGIES FOR Cu^{2+} IN K.J./MOLE

C_{sol}	C (electrolyte)				
	0.2M	0.3M	0.4M	0.5M	0.6M
1%	14.446	17.25	20.013	19.324	19.69
1.5%	13.359	17.15	16.247	15.66	16.67
2%	16.189	17.309	18.078	17.58	15.93

The analytical method results :

The decrease in the concentration of (Cu^{2+}) ions with time, for the different concentrations of sol and electrolyte is shown in Figures (1, 2). From these figures, it is quite evident that the rate of gel formation (the exchange process between Na^+ ions in the sol and Cu^{2+} ions in the electrolyte) is greater at first and then it decreases. Two definite slopes of the linear relation ($-dC/dt$) are recognized on these curves. The first slope is much greater than the second one. This means that the rate of gel growth i.e., the rate of ion exchange, or, the rate of the formation of the primary gel membrane (the most outer membrane which will be formed promptly at the moment of contact between the sol and electrolyte) is much higher at first, and then it decreases and that decrease becomes almost constant. At the

early stages of gel formation the rate was found to depend on both Cu^{2+} ion and sol concentrations. The second slope was found to depend only on the sol concentration. This fact can be explained on the basis of the diffusion control of the exchange process.

The formation of the primary gel membrane does not need considerable diffusion of the cations (Cu^{2+}) inside the sol, thus this process depends on both electrolyte and sol concentrations. It is faster in the higher electrolyte, and lower sol concentrations. Further growth of the gel takes place by the diffusion of the Cu^{2+} cations, through this primary membrane. The last process is greatly hindered by the viscosity of the sol, and the compactness of the already formed gel membrane. That is why, the rate of gel formation (second rate), is almost independent of the electrolyte concentration, and oppositely proportional to the sol concentration, due to the marked dependence of the viscosity on the sol concentration.

By plotting $\log \frac{\sigma_0 - \sigma_1}{\Delta t}$ versus $\frac{1}{T}$, straight

lines were obtained indicating the validity of our suggestion that the change of density with time can be considered as a measure of the gel growth rate.

Thus, the suggested technique and calculations may be of significant value in the kinetic studies of sol-gel transformation processes.

References

1. G. F. FISCHER and H. DORFEL, *Z. Physik Chem.*, 1955, 301, 224; *Z. Physik Chem.*, 1955, 302, 186.
2. H. THIELE, *Z. Naturforschung*, 1948, 36, 778.
3. H. THIELE, *Koll. Z.*, 1954, 136, 80.
4. H. THIELE and MICKE, *Koll. Z.*, 1948, 111, 73.
5. H. THIELE and L. LANGEMACK, *Natur. Wissensch.*, 1956, 43, 56; *Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1956, 206, 394.
6. H. THIELE and KIENAST, *Koll. Z.*, 1952, 127, 134.
7. H. THIELE and HALLICH, *Koll. Z.*, 1957, 136, 44.
8. A. AWAD and F. EL-CHEIKH, *Revue Roumaine de Chemie*, 1977.
9. A. AWAD, Dissertation Kiel, 1966.
10. W. SCOTT and H. FURMAN, *Standard methods of Chemical Analysis*, (Van. Nostrand, New York) 1952.